

GRAMMATICAL OPPOSITION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article provides information on the history and description of oppositions. The factual materials collected from English and Uzbek languages were classified based on the grammatical theory and analyzed. As a result of the analysis, the differences between the English and Uzbek languages have been revealed.

Key words: Grammatical opposition, opposeme, gradual opposition, equipollent opposition

Grammatical oppositions constitute grammatical categories. The principle parts of speech in English (the noun, the verb, the adjective and the adverb) have each a number of grammatical forms of the same word opposed to each other: different numbers and cases of nouns, different tenses, aspects, voices or moods of verbs, different degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs. It is on the basis of such oppositions that grammatical categories appear. The term category was introduced more than two thousand years ago by Aristotle. V.N. Yartseva¹ gives the following definition: the grammatical category is a generalized abstract meaning systematically expressed in the language by the opposition of definite forms of the same word.

A word might have multiple meanings according to grammar. One way to arrange many oppositions of different forms to the same form of this term is to make them obvious and unambiguous. Consider the following: the verb "runs" has multiple grammatical meanings: it is in the present tense, singular, third person, non-continuous aspect, indicative mood, etc. One might isolate each of these interpretations in an opposition:

(I) run / (he) runs (the 3rd person);

(they) run / (he) runs (singular);

(he) ran / (he) runs (the present tense);

(he) is running / (he) runs (the non-continuous aspect);

¹ В.Н.Ярцева. Взаимоотношение грамматики и лексики в системе языка. Москва. – 1968.– С.45.

(*They insisted that he) run / (he) runs* (the indicative mood).

In each of the pairs above the two members of the opposition are the forms of the same word *to run* identical in all respects but one: the very grammatical meaning we want to single out. These pairs are grammatical oppositions and each of the forms in a pair is an opposeme.

Oppositions in English typically consist of two opposemes. They are opposites in a binary system. However, oppositions consisting of three, four, or more members can be found, such as three cases of Russian nouns, three degrees of comparison (green, greener, greenest), or three people of personal pronouns (we, you, they). In addition to differing in the number of opposemes, oppositions can have three distinct characteristics. The eminent Russian linguist N.S. Trubetsky asserts that oppositions might be privative, equipollent, and gradual.

The level of intensity (degree) of the same define varies among the opposemes in the gradual opposition, such as the adjectives indicating temperature *cool – cold – warm – hot* (a more minute transition from heat to cold: *hot – warm – tepid – lukewarm – mild – fresh – cool – chilly – frosty – icy*).

Each opposeme in the equipollent opposition has its own characteristics, e.g. the Uzbek language past tense *keldim* shows the process before the moment of speech and future *kelaman*– after the moment of speech.

Just one opposeme in a privative opposition reveals meaning; the other, for example, has no meaning at all, such as *bad / not bad* or *I spoke of having done it (before) / I spoke of doing it (before, at the moment of speech, or after the speech moment)*.

R.Jacobson², L.S. Barkhudarov³ construct the framework of English language structure on double privative resistances. The opposeme which communicates the important meaning in a privative restriction is solid, or seriously, the other part of the restriction being powerless, or broad. In this way, plural of the things is the solid part (boys are, individuals are), particular is the frail one (a boy is, water is). The possessive case of the things could be solid part but the common case is the powerless one (the boy's book/the book). The non stop viewpoint alludes to the non-continuous perspective of verbs as solid and frail opposemes (The boy is running rapidly/ the boys runs rapidly).

² R.Jacobson. Избранные работы. Москва. Прогресс.-1985.– с71

³ Barkhudarov L. S. Yazyk i perevod (Voprosy obshchei i chastnoi teorii perevoda) [Language and Translation (Questions of general and particular translation theory)] / L. S. Barkhudarov. – M.: URSS, 2010. – 240 s. [in Russian].

On the off chance that we take up the final illustration, able to see that as it were is running communicates the thought of a concrete activity restricted in time and spoken to in its advancement but runs may render any way the activity takes place. The meaning of the solid part of the restriction is exceptionally particular, so it is utilized or may be rarely. The powerless part of the restriction has less confinements and it is utilized more regularly. Within the English content there are more verbs within the non-continuous frame, things within the particular and within the common case than their opposites.

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